

Using Interactive Activities in Teaching Short Stories

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Abstract

In the field of foreign language learning and teaching nowadays, literature is used as a tool to teach both basic language skills (i.e. reading, writing, speaking and listening) and language areas (i.e. vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation). Among different types of literary texts, short story is a supreme resource for observing not only language but life itself. It mirrors and illuminates human lives. So teachers who teach literature need to equip their students with the knowledge, skills and understanding they need to be able to live and function in society. In this paper, some innovative strategies of engaging students in activities, based on Bloom's (1956) taxonomy and Bottino's (1999) model, are presented. These different types of activities on the short story "The Destructors" by Greene (1954) are used to engage 98 third year English specialization students in learning a short story. The result is that they are motivated to learn a short story and they came to know the impacts of learning a short story.

Introduction

Literature is used as a tool to teach both basic language skills (i.e. reading, writing, speaking and listening) and language areas (i.e. vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation) in foreign language learning and teaching nowadays. Among different types of literary texts, short story is a supreme resource for observing not only language but life itself as it reflects human lives in the real life situation. So teachers who teach literature need to point out their students the knowledge, skills and understanding they need to be able to live and function in society. While they appreciate the literature text, they must have the good command of English. To do all these, students should be interested in learning short stories and after that they could extend their thought to the real life situation. In the past, traditional method, talk and chalk, is used to teach a short story and most of the students think it is boring. So the researcher wants her students to enjoy learning a short story, to have good language skills and to know the impacts of learning a short story. Activities that can attract students' attention on the short story are needed. So some innovative strategies of engaging students in learning a short story, based on Bloom's (1956) taxonomy and Bottino's (1999) model, on the short story "The Destructors" by Greene (1954) are used in the researcher's classroom and presented in this paper.

Theoretical background

Short Story

According to Sage (1987), short stories are supreme resource for observing not only language but life itself and it mirrors and illuminates human lives. Teachers need to equip students with knowledge, skills and understanding to live in society.

According to study.com, a short story typically takes the form of a brief fictional work, usually written in prose the earliest precursors to the short story can be found in the oral storytelling tradition. Anecdotes, fables, fairy tales and parables are all examples of the oral storytelling tradition that shaped the short story.

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Framework of three models

Bottino (1999) mentioned that teaching of literature can be seen within the framework of three models: the cultural model, the language model and the personal growth model.

The cultural model

The cultural model is seen as a means of transmitting ideas and feelings in the target language and as a way in which students encounter a wider variety of words and expressions. Through this model, students learn about culture and ideology of others. It is also sometimes seen as centering more on knowledge about texts with not much time being given to individual texts.

The language model

In the language model, some favour the teaching of literature for its use in language development. There are those who use literature as a tool to teach certain vocabulary or structure. It is often language teacher's wish to reveal examples of good use of language. Many believe that the students have much to gain in terms of language development by being given such examples, but they emphasize that the main purpose of literature teaching is to enable the student to find his own way into a text. In this language-based model, the activities are learner-centered. The focus is often on the way language is used, how linguistic forms convey literary meanings and going beyond the literal interpretation of the lines.

The personal growth model

The object of the third model, that of personal growth, has been termed by some as an engagement with the reading of literary texts, or an engagement not for the sake of getting through exams, but as a genuine liking for literature not confined solely to the classroom. Like the language model, this model is more student-centered. Its aim is to motivate the students to read by selecting themes, to a large extent, related to their own personal experiences. It is sometimes anti analytical and many describe its purpose as one of reading literature in order to make their text their own. Students are also encouraged to evaluate what they read for themselves and distinguish the merits of the works they read

Research Methodology

Blooms Taxonomy

Fig. 1. Bloom's Taxonomy (1956)

Bloom's Taxonomy, The Cognitive Process Dimension was developed by Benjamin Bloom in 1956. It helps to develop vitally important thinking skills in the students. There is a hierarchy of six levels of thinking which start with lower-order thinking at the bottom and end with higher-order thinking at the top. These six levels are remembering or knowledge, understanding or comprehension, application, analysis, evaluation and creation. These six levels have been adapted for classroom use as a planning tool. It is a classification of the different objectives and skills that educators set for their students.

The first level of Bloom's Taxonomy is to Remember.

That is the Knowledge remembering previously learned material; recall (facts or whole theories); bringing to mind.

- Who discovered the structure of DNA?
- What are the characteristics of a vector?

The second level of Bloom's Taxonomy is to Understand.

That is Comprehension grasping the meaning of material; interpreting (explaining or summarizing); predicting outcome and effects (estimating future trends).

- Summarize the process of photosynthesis.
- Distinguish between velocity and speed.

The third level of Bloom's Taxonomy is to Apply.

This is Application ability to use learned material in a new situation; apply rules laws, methods, and theories.

- Given the shape of a lot and the village setback conditions, what is the largest size one-story home you can build on the lot?
- Calculate the net force in this problem.

The fourth level of Bloom's Taxonomy is to Analyze.

Analysis is breaking down into parts; understanding organization, clarifying, concluding.

- What are the facts and opinions in the article we read?
- Diagram the chapter using a concept map.

The fifth level of Bloom's Taxonomy is to Evaluate.

Evaluation ability is to judge value for purpose; base on criteria; support judgment with reason.

- Rate the arguments for a heliocentric and geocentric view of the universe.
- Justify the use of Newton's Second Law versus Work-Energy in the solution to the problem.

The sixth level of Bloom's Taxonomy is to Create.

This level is Generating new ideas, products, or ways of viewing things, Designing, constructing, planning producing and inventing.

- Design a building to house your study.
- Invent a test that would show that the earth rotates.

Synopsis of a short story "The Destructors"

"The Destructors," a short story written by Graham Greene (1954) is used to teach Third Year and First Year Hons English Specialization students and it will be taken as an example short

story for this research paper. There are 98 Third Year and First Year Hons English Specialization students. They learned this short story by doing engaging activities.

The story is about a group of teenage boys who formed a gang named Wormsley Common gang. The gang members meet every day in a parking lot. Their town was bombed during World War II and everything in that area was destroyed but only Mr Thomas' house with minimal damage. The gang planned to do something bad to that house and at last their plan, destruction of Mr Thomas's house was successful. Greene (1954)'s interest in politics and intelligence work for the British government during World War II influence on this short story.

Engaging Activities

Activity I: The following elicited questions were asked to the students to recall their memory of childhood as the characters in the short story "The Destructors" are children. Students gave prompt responses to these questions.

Childhood

- Were you naughty when you were young?
- What was something naughty you did?
- Were you punished?
- How did you feel when you were punished?

Then students were also asked the following questions to recall their memory of forming groups as the characters in the short story "The Destructors" formed a gang. Students also gave prompt responses to these questions.

Childhood/Adolescent Gangs

- Did you belong to a gang or a particular group?
- Who was the group leader?
- Why did you choose them as a group leader?
- Who were the members?
- Were there any disagreements?
- Why do children/teenagers form gangs?

Activity II: Students were asked to sit in groups of four or five. They were informed that they were gangs. They were asked to think of the names of their gangs, for what reasons they form their gangs, role of gang members, then make their own posters of their gangs and to explain about their gangs to other gangs. The students happily formed gangs, made posters and reported back to the class. The class was noisy at that time.

Activity III: The next step is to read Part I of the short story "The Destructors," make notes and compare the gang in the short story "The Destructors" and their gangs. After that they were asked to report back the similarities and differences to the class. Here, students were very eager to know their similarities and differences.

Activity IV: The students were asked to read the given sentences which express the events in part I and decide these sentences 'True' or 'False.' Then teacher checked their answers. The students could answer easily and they were happy.

Activity V: The students were asked to read the events written on the strips of papers and arrange them in order. The ones who finished first and had correct answers got small prizes like chocolates or sweets from their teacher.

Activity VI: The students were given the dialogues from the short stories and discuss the meaning of the given dialogues in groups. Then they were asked to act out these dialogues in groups. Here, students enthusiastically performed in the dialogues as if they were characters in the short story.

Activity VII: The students, in groups, were given the small white board. They were asked to listen to the meaning or definition of a word, read out by the teacher and to write down the word on small whiteboard. The group who finished first and got the correct word will be the winner and was awarded. They had great interest and they competed each other very eagerly.

Activity VIII: In groups, the students were asked to make a poster of character sketch for the characters: Blackie, T / Trevor, Mike, Joe and Mr Thomas/ Old Misery.

- e.g. Mr Thomas – stingy – Old Misery was too mean to spend money on the property

They posted their posters on the wall and they were asked to continue the character development for the next parts like part II, III, etc. They will add their poster after reading every part of the short story. They argued their ideas to each other group and the class was noisy.

Activity IX: In groups, they were asked to write the prediction of “what will happen in the next part” and read out their prediction to the class. They can check whether their prediction is the same or different after reading next part. After learning every part, they were asked to do the same thing.

Activity X: Round-table Discussion

In this activity, students were asked to sit in group in the front of the class as a round-table discussion and were given the impromptu title to discuss within limited time. These titles are based on and related to the events and ideas in the short story. E.g.

- Why people vandalize public property and how society should deal with that
- The impact of wars on children
- The impact of different life experiences on children
- The importance of friendship in people’s lives

Discussion

All above mentioned are student engaging activities in teaching a short story. These ten activities are used to teach the third year and first year honours English specialization students for about fifteen periods (five periods per week). These activities reflect the six levels of Bloom’s taxonomy. It can be found in the following table.

Table 1. Activities and their levels in Blooms Taxonomy

Activity	Level (Blooms taxonomy)
I	Remembering
II	Remembering
III	Understanding
IV	Understanding
V	Application
VI	Application
VII	Analysis
VIII	Evaluation
IX	Evaluation
X	Creation

In Activity I, students recall their childhood memory and in Activity II, they formed gangs and made posters. So these two activities reflect Bloom's first level – remembering. In Activity III and IV, they compared their gang and the gang in the short stories and did True/False exercise to check their understanding of the short story. These two activities reflect the second level – Understanding. In Activity V, students rearrange the events in the short story and in Activity VI, they performed the acts. So these two activities reflect Bloom's third level – Application. In Activity VII, students thoroughly analyse the short story and it reflects the fourth level – Analysis. In Activity VIII and Activity IX, students evaluate the short story by doing prediction and writing character sketches as the students evaluate what they learned from this short story. The last activity Activity X reflects the last level creation as the students create their own opinion or ideas, based on the ideas they got from the short story.

All these activities are related to Bottino's (1999) model. These activities encourage the students to use the target language to express their own ideas like the cultural model is seen as a means of transmitting ideas and feelings in the target language and as a way in which students encounter a wider variety of words and expressions. All the interactive activities are also related to the cultural model because the teaching of literature is for its use in language development. There are those who use literature as a tool to teach certain vocabulary or structure. All the activities are related to the cultural model as of an engagement with the reading of literary texts.

According to the interview with the students, they said that this is the very first time they learned a short story in communicative ways. They really enjoyed doing all these activities and so they forgot the time while they were doing these activities. They were never bored. They waited for the next period and they were very anxious to participate in the coming activities. Moreover, they thought they were confident to speak English and they would not forget the events and the activities they did in the classroom. So they didn't need to learn this short story by-heart and they could write about that short story very well in the exam.

Conclusion

In this research paper, a short story “The Destructors” was taught to 98 third year and first year honors English specialization students by the researcher by using interactive activities which has never been used in the subjects’ literature classrooms. All these ten activities are related to Bloom’s taxonomy and every activity reflect every level of thinking. All these activities are also related to Bottino’s (1999) language framework. Moreover, based on interview result, students opinions on learning a short story by doing these activities are good and these activities can attract students’ attention on learning a short story and can raise their motivation to learn a short story. So these innovative strategies of engaging students in learning a short stories, based on Bloom’s (1956) taxonomy on the short story “The Destructors” by Greene (1954) are proved to be a great tool to teach short stories to students.

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